

Disintegration of Marriage as A Burden: A Study on Manju Kapur's *Custody*

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 8

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-2645

E-ISSN: 2582-3531

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Sindhiya Gaan, I.
"Disintegration of
Marriage as A Burden:
A Study on Manju
Kapur's Custody."
*Shanlax International
Journal of English*,
vol. 8, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 4-5.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3599828](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3599828)

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Manju Kapur's fifth novel *Custody* is basically set inside the thriving, higher-center-magnificence colonies of Delhi in the mid -90s, in opposition to the backdrop of the preliminary surge of foreign investment in India. ManjuKapur's novel reveals the unimagined doubts of marriage. The wife's experience of suffocation, the husband's fear of loneliness, and the steady transferring of the youngsters, like commodities, from one home to the other is expressed in the novel, *Custody*, which is true to the everyday angst of cutting-edge marriage with its burden of individualism.

Custody narrates the story of a couple Raman and Shagun and their two children, eight year antique Arjun and three year old Roohi, who loved a privileged lifestyles. Soon Shagun betrayed Raman with his boss, and that they in relationship. In Delhi Ishita's marriage collapsed due to the fact that she can't produce children. She tries to find some pleasure and an experience of identification in social work however she abandons it whilst she meets the divorced Raman.

The disintegration happens in *Custody* due to the extramarital affair thirst, which pays as an illegal guidelines remedy of a girl who can't conceive, and the converting parenting scenario in center elegance Indian homes. Shagun, the inexperienced-eyed lovely wife of Raman, falls in love together with his charismatic, good-looking boss Ashok Khanna, who wasn't in love earlier and later is determined to possess the girl. It does no longer be counted to him how but he goes approximately conquering Shagun's mind, body, and soul like a pro, persuasive marketer.

Throughout the novel, a true story of a present day marriage that exists around us. This is genuine in nowadays world. Kapurnovels voices out for the youngsters and shed mild on their situation while dad and mom replace by way of lawyers and fanatics. ManjuKapur sketches about ladies centered topics takes on to give up a long time marriage, divorce and the subsequent custody war. She shows how a modern daywomen can think of now not looking to stay in a

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relationship and look for liberation and happiness out of doors her home or even that did not make one desires to hate her for her choices.

Kapur's novel exhibits not of the disintegration inside the own family but also the existence of women, their warfare for primary rights, quest for identification, and survival. She portrays how girls are affected by monetary and socio-cultural risks within the male governed society. Custody is the riveting story of the way family-love can fall apart into an obsession to own children, frame, and soul, as well as a chilling critique of the Indian judicial gadget. It disintegrate, social hypocrisies and battles for youngsters that intertwine with suffering and conflict for you to depict an international fact of politics of possessiveness and unequal strength members of the family in normative patriarchal households which is a website for constraint, oppression, violence, possessiveness, and disintegration.

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